

Maulana Hasrat Mohani: A brief life sketch and Contribution to Swadeshi Movement

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Abstract:

One of the most notable and significant movements in the series of movements that led to India's independence was the Swadeshi movement. Indians were given a forum by the Swadeshi movement to come together under the banner of nationalism and demonstrate their strength against colonial rule. Many Known freedom fighters were part of this movement which was an important event in India's history. Every community has contributed to the struggle for the Independence of India and their contribution is well documented. Like other communities in India Muslims too have contributed to the freedom movement but most of the Muslim freedom fighters have faded into oblivion. There is a huge list of lesser-known Muslim freedom fighters among which one prominent name is Maulana Hasrat Mohani. This paper will throw light on his life, and his revolutionary temper and will analyze his role in the Swadeshi movement.

Keywords: Swadeshi Movement, Maulana Hasrat Mohani, Freedom movements, Muslim Freedom fighters, Inquilab Zindabad, National movements

Introduction:

Maulana Hasrat Mohani was one of the prominent leaders on the scene of India's independence struggle. In the social, political, and cultural evolution of modern India, he occupies a major position. He was one of the most ardent leaders of the national movement. Maulana Hasrat Mohani was a fierce opponent of British authority and an advocate for his people's freedom. He wished to gain full freedom from the British. He was one of the early proponents of "Swaraj." The battle against the Britishers took place on numerous fronts. Some were using the power of the pen, some were on the streets, and some were using diplomacy. Maulana Hasrat Mohani engaged in combat on all three fronts. From the Swadeshi movement to the civil disobedience movement, he participated in practically every national movement. He was a historical stalwart who helped lay the groundwork for India's independence from the British Raj and later served as the cornerstone of the liberation movement.

Early life and beginning of political career:

Maulana, a well-known poet and prominent independence fighter, was born on January 1, 1875, in Mohan, in the Unnao region of United Province (modern-day Uttar Pradesh). Maulana was a poet who wrote under the pen name Mohani, which refers to his place of birth. Syed Fazal-ul-Hasan was actually his real name.¹ Maulana Hasrat Mohani, an alumnus of Aligarh's M.A.O. College, had strong ties to the Indian National Congress and had taken part in anti-British demonstrations even as a student. He was expelled from Aligarh College due to his political activity in support of the Congress. His decision to launch his well-known Urdu monthly magazine, Urdu-i-Mualla, without waiting for the results of his B.A. final examination is a strong indication of his keen interest in the nation's anti-

British political issues. Its inaugural issue was published in July 1903 from Aligarh, which served as something of the epicentre for Muslim intellectual activity in India at the time. Though it was a literary magazine for a while at first, political issues quickly took front stage.² He had been a fierce opponent of the British Raj since he was young. He loved his country and would gladly have participated in any anti-British demonstration. He always had a revolutionary mindset and was willing to make genuine sacrifices and commitments. Hasrat became a member of the Congress and went to the 1904 session. According to Syed Sulaiman Nadvi, Urdu-i-Mualla awoke Muslims before anyone else did. This young Aligarh graduate joined the Congress and attended its annual session in Bombay in 1904 as a delegate, during a period when Muslims were reluctant to enter politics. He stuck to his policy of attending Congress sessions until the split of congress in surat session.³

Partition of Bengal and Rise of the Swadeshi Movement:

One of the most significant incidents in colonial India was the division of Bengal, which had a significant impact on national movements. The intellectual revolutionaries at the vanguard of the freedom movement centred their efforts in Bengal. Bengal was to be divided according to a plan devised by Lord Curzon, the then Viceroy of India, in order to weaken the political opposition in the province. The core of Indian nationalism was thought to be strengthening at the time of partition, and it was anticipated that this would happen. According to Viceroy Lord Curzon (1899–1905), the goal was to "dethrone Calcutta" from its role as the hub from which the Congress party is controlled across Bengal and, in fact, all of India.⁴ Home Secretary Herbert Risley made this point clear in his note of 7 February 1904. "Bengal United is a

power". He argued; "Bengal divided will pull in several different ways."⁵

When the plans for partition were made public in December 1903, there was an instantaneous and unplanned uprising. On July 19, 1905, the decision to split Bengal was made public.⁶ A smaller-scale movement became a larger-scale Swadeshi movement. At a conference held at the town hall in Calcutta on August 7, 1905, the Swadeshi movement was formally declared, and the renowned boycott resolution was passed.⁷ The anti-partition movement helped to further unite the Bengalees after the division, rather than weakening and splitting them.⁸ Abdul Rasul, president of the Barisal conference, April 1906, put it: "What we could not have accomplished in 50 or 100 years, the great disaster, the partition of Bengal has done for us in six months. Its fruits have been the great national movement known as the Swadeshi movement."⁹

Role of Maulana Hasrat Mohani in the Swadeshi movement:

Maulana was a significant player in the Swadeshi movement because of his great work in promoting the boycott message. Maulana was among the pioneering figures who sought to incorporate ordinary Muslims into the liberation movement. Maulana Hasrat Mohani exerted greater effort than before to educate people about the boycott and to promote Swadeshi products. Hasrat travelled far and wide throughout the towns of western Uttar Pradesh and eastern Punjab in those days to preach and popularise his ideas among the masses, especially Muslims.¹⁰

Following the division of Bengal, the Congress initiated the 'Swadeshi movement' across the nation in an attempt to undermine the government and make the public aware of the benefits of products made in Swadeshi. Hasrat Mohani backed this Swadeshi movement with great enthusiasm. One of his professors in school, who was a staunch advocate of Khadi, had instilled a deep affection for Swadeshi items in him. He went to the All-India Industrial Conference that was held at Banaras in 1905. He has been a devoted follower of the movement ever since.¹¹ Maulana propagated his views on the Swadeshi movement by using the power of the written word. In this regard, several pieces were published in his Urdu-i-Mualla. The country's citizens were urged in these articles to utilise homemade goods instead of British goods, citing this as the most efficient way to harm British interests in India. Hasrat encouraged Muslims in the nation to understand the importance of boycott movements and fully engage in these anti-British actions, particularly as the Swadeshi movement gained traction among the majority community.¹²

Maulana's fondness for Swadeshi products and the importance of supporting local companies

were taught to him by one of his teachers when he was a small child, and these principles have stuck with him ever since. He was quite inventive in spreading the word about embracing Swadeshi products and rejecting foreign goods, and he had original ideas concerning Swadeshi goods. From the outset, Maulana Hasrat was a staunch advocate of the Swadeshi movement. He did everything in his power to spread this movement and believed that it was the only way to advance the country's economy. He put a lot of effort into spreading these concepts among all Indians. His initial move was to stop importing products. He focused all of his efforts on spreading this movement and published articles for his newspaper. Among the Muslims who were with him and were impacted by his works, he was more successful. Consequently, a sizeable portion of the population stopped using imported goods. Still, Hasrat did not think his work was good enough. He desired to take on more work. As a result, he opened a "Swadeshi Store" in the Aligarh neighbourhood of Russell Ganj and filled it with various produced goods from India that were needed on a daily basis.¹³

Hasrat saw Swadeshi from a distinct angle. "Swadeshi" is anything made in the country, according to him. He took the same position with regard to attire. He vehemently disagreed with other national leaders, saying that hand-woven cloth was not the only type that qualified as Swadeshi and that Indian fabric created in mills was equally as Swadeshi as Khaddar. Even if foreign capital was employed in the production process, he still regarded as Swadeshi items those manufactured with labour and materials sourced locally.

In the ensuing years, Hasrat exerted more effort than ever to disseminate the boycott message and convert people, especially Muslims, to Swadeshi products. In this regard, he even went so far as to obtain acclaim from the religious authorities of both Muslims and Hindus. His sole purpose in obtaining printed fatwas from various Ulama was to draw the Muslim populace to the Swadeshi movement. He went one step further in the April 1913 Urdu-i Mualla issue, saying that the boycott of foreign goods and the Swadeshi movement had religious legitimacy and that early Islamic history provided an analogous model, based on the Holy Quran and Hadees. Through the same issue, we also learn about Hasrat's travels across the nation to spread awareness of the movements. The major cities of the western U.P. and Punjab that he visited were Bareilly, Moradabad, Meerut, Deoband, Saharanpur, Hardwar, Lahore, Amritsar, and Ludhiana. He spoke with people from various sections throughout this journey and urged them to come forward. He also conveyed to the general

Muslim populace that the Ulama supported the movements.¹⁴

Imprisonment:

Because of his political activity, Hasrat caused problems for the British and was twice imprisoned throughout his lifetime for his anti-British views. Shortly after the Surat Session, in April 1908, he penned an article in his Urdu-i Mualla titled "Educational Policy of Britishers in Egypt," in which he harshly criticised the British educational agenda. On June 22, 1908, he was taken into custody on seditious article writing accusations.¹⁵ Hasrat was sentenced to 500 rupees in fines and four years of hard work. Because Hasrat was unable to pay the five hundred rupees required to realise this charge, his rare book library was put up for auction for sixty rupees, with the proceeds going towards paying the fine.¹⁶ In or around April 1916, Hasrat was arrested a second time. He was made to labour for hours at the grinding wheel, crushing one maund of wheat every day for a year, and he was frequently confined in solitary confinement while incarcerated.¹⁷ He lost his father and suffered many humiliations while incarcerated, yet in spite of all of these hardships and atrocities, he continued to resist the British and pursue Swaraj.

Last Years:

He disagreed with the idea of splitting India. When the All India Muslim League passed the Pakistan Resolution at its Lahore session in March 1940, Hasrat made a concerted effort to stop the country's split. He made the decision to remain in India after Independence. Prior to his passing on May 13, 1951, in Lucknow, Maulana Hasrat Mohani lived a revolutionary life. He asked to be interred in the same city, adjacent to the grave of Maulana Abdul Wahab of Firangi Mahal, his spiritual mentor.

Conclusion:

Maulana Hasrat Mohani was an outstanding liberation warrior. He stayed dedicated to the goal of an independent India and contributed significantly to nearly every national movement. He organized Muslims to fight the British Raj and made an effort to integrate them into the national movement. In addition to being a fierce opponent of the British Raj, he was an excellent poet. He inspired readers to revolutionize with his words in the same way that he inspired people to take revolution on the streets. He created "Inquilab Zindabad," one of the most famous slogans of the freedom movement, which was later adopted and immortalized by Bhagat Singh. This phrase is still used in today's protests across the subcontinent. Till his last days, he remained an obedient servant of India. His valuable contribution and sacrifice in the freedom struggle shall be remembered forever and his revolutionary

temper may serve as an inspiration for generations to come.

References:

1. Syed Ubaidur Rahman, *Muslim freedom fighters: Contribution of Indian Muslims in Independence movement*, Global Media Publication, Delhi, 2018, p 65
2. Mohammad Arshad, *Hasrat Mohani: A critical appraisal of his political career and ideology*, Department of History, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, 2009, p 2
3. Syed Sulaiman Nadvi, *Hasrat ki siyasi zindagi*, Niyaz Fatehpur, Karachi, 1952, p 112
4. Bipan Chandra, *India's struggle for Independence*, Penguin books, Gurgaon, 2016, pp 124-125
5. Sekhar Bandyopadhyay, *From plassey to partition and after*, Orient Blackswan, Hyderabad, 2020, p 253
6. Bipan Chandra, *op.cit*, p 126
7. *Ibid*, p 126
8. Sekhar Bandyopadhyay, *op.cit*, p 254
9. Bipan Chandra, *op.cit*, p 127
10. Mohammad Arshad, *op.cit*, pp 3-4
11. Urdu-i-mualla, Urdu press, Aligarh, March and April 1906, pp 83-86
12. Mohammad Arshad, *op.cit*, p 43
13. Arif Hasvi, *Halat-i-Hasrat*, Maulana Hasrat Mohani memorial Library and Trust, Karachi, 1993, pp 52-53
14. Urdu-i-mualla, Urdu Press, Aligarh, April 1913, p 25
15. Urdu-i-mualla, Urdu Press, Aligarh, January 1910, p 9
16. G. Allana, *Eminent Muslim Freedom Fighters*, Neeraj Publishing House, Delhi 1969, p 217
17. *Ibid*, p 218